

A MORE EFFICIENT METHOD FOR FLEXURAL VIBRATION OF COMPOSITE PLATES WITH CRACKS, CUTOUT AND STIFFENERS

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ABSTRACT

A numerical method which combines the flexibility of finite element techniques and the computational accuracy of the Rayleigh Ritz scheme for solving vibration problems of plate is presented. The method involves sub-division of the plates into appropriate rectangular segments in order to approximate the deflection function by sets of orthogonal polynomials. Natural frequency of isotropic and orthotropic plates with cracks and cutouts obtained using the present method are compared with the existing analytical and numerical results, and the agreement is found to be very good.

INTRODUCTION

The present paper described an accurate numerical method for the solution of free vibration problem of plates with cracks and cutouts. In this method, the flexibility of finite element techniques is combined with the accuracy of the Rayleigh Ritz scheme to achieve computation efficiency. To analyse plate problems of complex geometry, the plate is first discretized into appropriate rectangular segments as in the finite element method. Simple deflection expressions in the form of orthogonal polynomial are derived for each segment. In between segments, geometrical continuity are enforced at evenly spaced discrete points to link the segments together. Minimising the energy functional corresponding to the assumed deflection function will give the natural frequencies of vibration. The formulation of the Rayleigh Ritz method using orthogonal polynomial function was first suggested by Bhat [1]. The subsequent works of Dickinson and Blasio [2], Lam and Hung [3] further verified its validity and accuracy for a variety of plate problems involving free edges. The relative ease with which these functions may be derived and manipulated, prompted their use in the present method.

NUMERICAL FORMULATION

To demonstrate the numerical procedures, a rectangular plate with a centrally located rectangular cutout is considered. Fig. 1 shows the geometry and dimensions of the plate. Taking the advantage of geometrical symmetry, vibration mode symmetric and anti-symmetric about the axes can be evaluated by considering only the lower quadrant of the plate domain. The lower quadrant is further divided into smaller rectangular segments. Appropriate deflection function for each segment are chosen accordingly.

Depending on the mode of vibration considered, the edges along the axes of symmetry, $x = a/2$ and $y = b/2$, will be subjected to different restraints. Solutions for the symmetric modes will be obtained from the conditions of zero slope and shear force along the axis of symmetry. For the anti-symmetric modes, the requirement of zero displacement and moment are imposed.

The deflection function assumed for each segments are in the following form:

$${}^{(e)}W_{(x,y)} = \sum_m \sum_n {}^{(e)}A_{mn} {}^{(e)}\phi_m(x) {}^{(e)}\psi_n(y) \quad (1)$$

where ϕ_m and ψ_n are polynomial functions satisfying at least the geometrical boundary conditions of the respective segments. The superscript (e) represents the segment number.

The polynomial function $\phi_m(x)$ (and $\psi_n(y)$), assumed in the deflection are the characteristic orthogonal polynomial function generated using the Gram-Schmidt process. Starting with an initial polynomial $\phi_1(x)$ satisfying the geometrical and natural boundary conditions of the equivalent beam function, the subsequent terms are generated using the recursive formula (see Ref. 4).

The deflection function of the adjacent segments will have one of the two polynomial sets, $\phi_m(x)$ or $\psi_n(y)$ in common. By enforcing continuity of transverse deflection at evenly spaced discrete points along the interconnecting lines, the undetermined coefficients ${}^{(e)}A_{mn}$, $e = 1, 2, 3$ of the deflection function for each segment will be coupled together. Taking segment 1 and 2 as an illustration, the following condition is imposed,

$${}^{(1)}W_{(x,y)} = {}^{(2)}W_{(x,y)} \text{ at evenly spaced discrete point } P_t, \quad (2)$$

where $t = 1, 2, \dots, N$.

Upon substitution of the co-ordinate values of P_t into (3), the following matrix expression is formulated,

$$[\text{CONT}(1)] {}^{(1)}A_{mn} = [\text{CONT}(2)] {}^{(2)}A_{mn} \quad (3)$$

where $[\text{CONT}(e)]^T = [M_1, M_2 \dots M_t \dots M_N]$

and $M_t = \left\{ \phi_1(X_t)\psi_1(Y_1) \quad \phi_1(X_t)\psi_2(Y_2) \dots \phi_N(X_t)\psi_N(Y_t) \right\}$

The coupled deflection function for each segment is substituted into the following Strain and Kinetic energy expressions,

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \iint [D_{11}W_{xx}^2 + D_{22}W_{yy}^2 + 2D_{12}W_{xx}W_{yy} + 4D_{66}W_{xy}^2] dx dy \quad (4)$$

$$T = \frac{\rho h w^2}{2} \iint W^2 dx dy \quad (5)$$

where the integration are to be carried out over the domain of the segment considered, and D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{12} , D_{66} are the usual material properties.

The total strain and kinetic energies of the entire domain are assumed to be the sum of the contribution from each segment. Minimising the resulting functional

$(U_{Total} - T_{Total})$ with respect to the undetermined coefficients of segment 1.

$(1)A_{mn}$, leads to the eigenvalue equation,

$$\sum_m \sum_n [K_{mnij} - \Omega^2 M_{mnij}] (1)A_{mn} = 0 \quad (6)$$

where $\Omega = (\rho h \omega^2 a^4 / D_{22})^{1/2}$ and K_{mnij} , M_{mnij} are the total stiffness and mass matrices of the plate considered. Solving equation (6) yields the natural frequency of the plate at the specific mode of vibration considered.

FREE VIBRATION OF RECTANGULAR PLATES WITH CUTOUTS

To check the validity of the present method, the experimental results obtained by Aksu et al [4] for isotropic rectangular plate with single or double cutouts are listed for comparison. Fig. 2 shows the geometries and dimensions of the plates studied and the number of segments considered in the analysis. The numerical results obtained are compared in Table 1. The agreement is good for single and double cutouts cases. It is noted that the present method yields slightly higher frequency as compared to the experimental results. It may be due to the difficulty in imposing a perfectly clamped boundary condition in experiment. Free vibration of specially orthotropic square plates with center cutout has also been studied (Figure 3). The method has also been extended to plates with cracks and stiffeners and good results are obtained.

CONCLUSION

A simple numerical method combining the versatility of the finite element techniques and the computational efficiency of the Rayleigh Ritz procedure has been proposed to predict the natural frequencies of some complex plate problems. The numerical results obtained for plates with cutouts subjected to various combination of boundary conditions are compared with that reported by other investigators, and they are found to be in good agreement. The method has also been extended to plates with cracks, stiffeners and having mixed boundary conditions.

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Table 1
 Frequency parameters of a C-SS-C-SS isotropic rectangular plate
 with double cutouts ($\nu = 0.3$)

Mode shape	Ω		Frequency in Hz		
	Aksu [8]	Present	Aksu [8]	Present	Experiment [8]
	47.86	49.26	124.08	127.71	127
	93.62	97.97	242.71	253.99	246
	122.04	130.82	316.41	339.17	324
	151.95	160.35	393.92	415.70	398

Fig. 1 Geometry and dimensions of plate with centrally located rectangular cutout.

Fig. 2 Geometry and dimensions of plates with rectangular cutout.

Fig. 3 Fundamental frequency parameter for a fully clamped orthotropic square plate.

• Rajamani, — Present method